

Ligand Scrambling in Bismuth(III) Dithiocarbamates

G. SOUNDARARAJAN and M. SUBBAIYAN

Department of Analytical Chemistry, University of Madras, Guindy, Madras-600 025

Dithiocarbamate moieties are found to be labile in bismuth(III) dithiocarbamates as in other metal dithiocarbamates. Unsymmetric mixed ligand dithiocarbamates are formed by ligand scrambling while mixing simple symmetrical dithiocarbamates in non-polar solvents. Elemental analyses, electronic, ir and nmr spectral studies showed that these complexes are identical with those derived from halo bisdithiocarbamates.

LIGAND lability in a number of transition metal complexes with S-donor chelating ligands has been reported^{1,2}. Formation of mixed ligand metal dithiocarbamates by this ligand lability and their exchange kinetics have been reported by some HPLC studies^{3,4}. Ligand scrambling and the consequent formation of mixed ligand dithiocarbamates have been studied by Beinrohr and Garaj⁵ and Duffy⁶ with ¹H nmr spectroscopy. HPLC studies have shown that the dithiocarbamate moiety is more labile in bivalent metal chelates than in trivalent metal chelates. Though Stary⁷ reported the formation of mixed dithiocarbamate-dithizone complexes for group V-a elements, ligand exchange in their tris-dithiocarbamates has not been studied in detail. Kheiri *et al.*⁸ prepared a number of mixed ligand bismuth(III) dithiocarbamates through halo bisdithiocarbamates of Bi(III). It is found that even simple mixing of symmetric bismuth(III) dithiocarbamates resulted in the formation of ternary (mixed ligand) complexes in non-polar solvents. Elemental analysis and other spectral studies showed that these complexes are identical with those obtained by Kheiri *et al.*

Experimental

Sodium salts of the dithiocarbamic acids were prepared by standard methods^{9,10}. Neutral tris-chelates and iodo bischelates of Bi(III) were prepared from them as reported¹¹.

Preparation of mixed ligand dithiocarbamates of Bi(III):

Method A (Kheiri et al.⁸): Mixed ligand complexes were prepared by refluxing iodo bis(dithiocarbamates) of Bi(III) in CHCl₃ with appropriate sodium salt of the dithiocarbamic acid in ethanol, strictly adopting the reported procedure⁸. The elemental analyses of the products agreed with those reported by Kheiri *et al.*⁸.

Method B: 20 millimole of a Bi(III) dithiocarbamate (which is to be present in greater proportion) in 20 ml benzene was mixed with 10 millimole (in 10 ml benzene) of another Bi(III) dithiocarbamate with different N-alkyl substituent. The mixture was stirred magnetically for 45 min at 40-50° in a FB flask fitted with a reflux condenser. The solution was then concentrated by evaporation

under low pressure (0.01 Torr) and spotted on preparative tlc plates (50-60 μl solution per spot) and developed with xylene. After development, the thin layer portions corresponding to the ternary mixed ligand complexes were scrapped off, the complexes extracted with minimum quantity of benzene under inert atmosphere and the solvent was removed in a vacuum evaporator. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in benzene. Elemental analyses (C and H) were performed with Perkin Elmer 240 B analyser. Nitrogen was estimated by micro Kjeldahl method and sulphur by gravimetry as BaSO₄. Bismuth was estimated by EDTA titration after acid digestion of the sample.

Electronic spectra were obtained with Beckmann model 25 UV-visible spectrophotometer at 29° in benzene solution. IR spectra were recorded with Perkin-Elmer 199 spectrometer scanning the region 4000-200 cm⁻¹ in KBr pellets. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian 60 MHz instrument in CCl₄ with TMS as the internal standard.

Silica gel G supplied by B.D.H. was employed for preparing thin layers. All chemicals employed in this study were of analytical grade.

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analyses for the mixed ligand bismuth(III) dithiocarbamates (Table 1) prepared by methods A and B are in good agreement. Complexes prepared by both the methods decompose before melting. Results of tlc studies (Table 2) are also in good agreement. Their mobilities are intermediate with respect to the parent compounds. Pale yellow streaks observed preceding the zones may be due to their partial disintegration into symmetric complexes. Formation of diagonally arranged spots in two dimensional tlc with moderately polar eluents CCl₄-CHCl₃ (1:1), CCl₄-CH₂Cl₂ (1:1), etc. support this as observed earlier⁸. In solution, these complexes are stable only for 25-30min, then begin to disintegrate and reach equilibrium after 2-3 hr. The increasing polarity of the solvent accelerates this disintegration in the order xylene < toluene < benzene < chloroform < methylene-dichloride.

According to Moriyasu and Hashimoto⁴, the exchange kinetics is dependant only on statistical

SOUNDARARAJAN & SUBBAIYAN : LIGAND SCRAMBLING IN BISMUTH(III) DITHIOCARBAMATES

TABLE 1

Complex	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)					M. Wt. Found (Calcd.)	Yield ^a %
	C	H	N	S	Bi		
Bi[S ₂ CN(C ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₂ [S ₂ CN(C ₂ H ₇) ₂]	29.98	5.07	6.22	28.31	30.41	742.24	38
Bi(de) ₂ (dpr)	(29.94)	(5.03)	(6.16)	(28.22)	(30.65)	(681.86)	
Bi[S ₂ CN(C ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₂ [S ₂ CN(CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₅) ₂]	38.62	4.42	5.47	24.74	26.75	849.84	40
Bi(de) ₂ (dbz)	(38.59)	(4.41)	(5.40)	(24.73)	(26.87)	(777.94)	
Bi[S ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₂] ₂ [S ₂ CN(C ₂ H ₅) ₂]	30.15	4.48	6.30	28.42	30.65	683.42	25
Bi(Pip) ₂ (de)	(30.12)	(4.46)	(6.20)	(28.38)	(30.83)	(677.83)	
Bi[S ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₂] ₂ [S ₂ CN(C ₂ H ₇) ₂]	32.39	4.83	5.91	27.31	29.56	733.34	20
Bi(Pip) ₂ (dpr)	(32.33)	(4.85)	(5.95)	(27.26)	(29.61)	(705.88)	
Bi[S ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₂] ₂ [S ₂ CN(CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₅) ₂]	40.48	4.24	5.21	24.10	25.97	820.25	20
Bi(Pip) ₂ (dbz)	(40.43)	(4.27)	(5.24)	(23.99)	(26.06)	(801.96)	

a - prepared by the method B.

TABLE 2—hR_f VALUES FROM TLC STUDY

Complexes	Eluent/Method ^a					
	CHCl ₃ - C ₆ H ₁₄ (1 : 1)		CHCl ₃ - CCl ₄ (1 : 1)		Xylene	
	A	B	A	B	A	B
Bi(dMe) ₂ dpr	13.0	11.8	29.0	27.0	15.0	12.8
Bi(dMe) ₂ dbu	25.0	25.0	45.0	43.3	60.2	57.9
Bi(dMe) ₂ dbz	8.2	7.9	36.2	35.4	—	—
Bi(de) ₂ dpr	20.2	18.8	22.0	22.7	22.0	20.4
Bi(de) ₂ dbu	25.6	23.8	33.3	31.1	49.3	47.7
Bi(de) ₂ dbz	13.3	9.9	30.5	32.1	58.2	54.6
Bi(Pip) ₂ dpr	15.4	13.1	35.0	33.6	16.0	16.5
Bi(Pip) ₂ dbu	29.3	28.0	50.0	51.0	45.0	43.2
Bi(Pip) ₂ dbz	20.0	15.9	42.3	38.2	50.1	45.5
Bi(dMe) ₂		1.9		2.8		0
Bi(de) ₂		7.8		14.0		3.7
Bi(dpr) ₂		21.4		38.3		31.2
Bi(dbu) ₂		53.9		71.0		71.7
Bi(dbz) ₂		24.8		55.1		61.9
Bi(Pip) ₂		7.6		12.2		8.4

Layer thickness 0.25 mm, activated at 120° for 30 min. Ascending development at 29° in closed chambers preequilibrated with eluent vapours. Solvent migration upto 11 cm from the spotted regions. dMe = dimethyl, de = diethyl, dpr = di- π -propyl, dbu = di-*n*-butyl, dbz = dibenzyl, Pip = piperidyl.

a (A, B) = Methods of preparation of mixed ligand complexes as detailed in text.

factor. Non-polar solvent molecules surrounding the ternary chelate molecule in solution may be presumed to prevent their collision with other chelate molecules which leads to disintegration.

Electronic spectra :

These ternary complexes show strong absorption in the region 38.2 to 39.0 kK due to π - π^* transition like simple symmetric trischelates⁶. All show shoulder peaks in the visible region 27.0 to 27.5 kK due to n - π^* transition (Table 3). The absorption peaks in the visible region are broadened in the mixed ligand complexes (Figs. 1 and 2), a fact not reported by Kheiri *et al.*

IR spectra :

IR spectral data of some of the mixed ligand complexes are presented in Table 4. The absorption due to "thioureide" (N - C) bond is observed in the region 1470-1500 cm⁻¹. As stated by Kheiri *et al.*⁶, the 'dtc' moiety present in major proportion determines the ir spectral characteristics. ν (C - S) absorptions are observed in the region 980-1000 cm⁻¹. However, these complexes show considerable shifts for ν (M-S) and chelate ring deformation absorption modes.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF MIXED LIGAND AND CORRESPONDING Tris COMPLEXES OF BISMUTH (III)

Complex	n - π^* transition in visible region kK (log ϵ)	
	method A	method B
Bi(dMe) ₂ dpr	27.4 (4.01)	27.4 (4.02)
Bi(dMe) ₂ dbu	27.4 (3.98)	27.5 (3.99)
Bi(dMe) ₂ dbz	27.5 (4.03)	27.5 (4.03)
Bi(de) ₂ dpr	27.5 (3.90)	27.5 (3.98)
Bi(de) ₂ dbu	27.4 (3.88)	27.4 (3.95)
Bi(de) ₂ dbz	27.2 (3.84)	27.4 (4.05)
Bi(Pip) ₂ de	[27.4 (4.04)] 27.5 (3.91)	27.4 (3.94)
Bi(Pip) ₂ dpr	[27.5 (3.92)] 27.4 (3.93)	27.4 (3.94)
Bi(Pip) ₂ dbu	27.5 (4.00)	27.5 (4.01)
Bi(Pip) ₂ dbz	27.4 (3.95) [27.4 (3.99)]	27.2 (3.97)
Bi(dme) ₂		27.5 (3.79)
Bi(de) ₂		27.4 (3.98)
Bi(dpr) ₂		27.4 (4.07)
Bi(dbu) ₂		27.4 (3.99)
Bi(dbz) ₂		27.0 (4.07)
Bi(Pip) ₂		27.4 (3.95)

All show strong absorbance in the uv region from 38.2 to 39.0 kK (log ϵ 4.8-4.95). Values in square brackets are those reported in reference 8.

TABLE 4—IR SPECTRAL DATA^a OF SOME MIXED LIGAND DITHIOCARBAMATES^b AND CORRESPONDING BISMUTH(III) *Tris* DITHIOCARBAMATES

	de	dpr	dbz	Pip	(de) ₂ dbz	(de) ₂ dpr	(Pip) ₂ dbz	(Pip) ₂ dpr
$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	1486 s	1478 s	1494 s 1465 m	1475 s	1488 s	1482 s	1470 s	1475 s
$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$	1266 s	1298 s 1205 m	1190 s	1210 s	1265 s 1190 m	1265 s 1200 m	1275 s 1210 m	1275 s 1215 m
$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$	979 s	958 s	990 s	960 s 1000 m	980 s	979 s	998 s 960 m	998 s 960 m
$\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ and chelate ring deformation	630 w 470 w	650 w 455 w	695 s 620 w 420 w	610 w 455 w	685 m 620 w 475 w	672 w 490 m	710 s 620 w 470 w	600 w 470 w

a—in KBr pellets.

b = Complexes prepared by method B.

s = strong; m = medium and w = weak.

TABLE 5—¹H NMR PARAMETERS FOR SOME MIXED LIGAND AND CORRESPONDING BISMUTH(III) *Tris* DITHIOCARBAMATES

Complex	Chemical shifts in τ values			Literature ^b	
	This work ^a A	B	C	A	B
Bi(de) ₂ dpr	de : 6.22 (q, 8p), dpr : 6.04 (m, 4p)	8.41 (t, 12p) 8.00 (m, 4p)	— 8.81 (t, 6p)	—	—
Bi(de) ₂ dbz	de : 6.15 (q, 8p), dbz : 4.93 (s, 4p)	8.66 (t, 12p), 2.63 (s, ϕ p)	—	6.15 (q, 8p), 4.91 (m, 4p)	8.65 (t, 12p), 2.63 (s, ϕ p)
Bi(Pip) ₂ de	Pip : 5.95 (m, 8p), de : 6.17 (q, 4p)	8.28 (m, 12p), 8.66 (t, 6p)	—	5.96 (m, 8p), 6.17 (q, 4p)	8.26 (m, 12p), 8.67 (t, 6p)
Bi(Pip) ₂ dpr	Pip : 5.77 (m, 8p), dpr : 6.11 (t, 4p)	7.95 (m, 12p), 7.96 (m, 4p)	8.70 (t, 6p)	—	—
Bi(Pip) ₂ dbz	Pip : 5.90 (m, 8p), dbz : 4.89 (s, 4p)	8.27 (m, 12p), 2.65 (s, ϕ p)	—	5.92 (m, 8p), 4.88 (s, 4p)	8.27 (m, 12p), 2.62 (s, ϕ p)

a : prepared by method B. b : From ref (8)—prepared by method A.

A, B and C are the α , β and γ positions of the protons with respect to N-atom.

s = singlet; t = triplet; q = quartet; m = multiplet; p = protons equivalent.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of symmetric bismuth(III) tris-dithiocarbamates.

1. $\text{Bi}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)_2]_3$ = $7.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$.
2. $\text{Bi}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2]_3$ = $5.7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$.
3. $\text{Bi}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2]_3$ = $7.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$.
4. $\text{Bi}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10})]_3$ = $3.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of mixed ligand bismuth(III) dithiocarbamates in the visible region.

1. $\text{Bi}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)_2]_2[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2]$ = $8.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$.
2. $\text{Bi}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)_2]_2[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2]$ = $5.7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$.
3. $\text{Bi}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10})]_2[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2]$ = $5.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$.
4. $\text{Bi}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10})]_2[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2]$ = $7.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$.

NMR spectra :

In Table 5 are presented the proton nmr data for some of the mixed ligand complexes prepared by method B along with those reported by Kheiri *et al*⁹. As observed by Kheiri *et al*, no new peaks were observed for these ternary complexes as against the observation made for iron(III) mixed ligand dithiocarbamates. However, considerable shifts of the signals, mostly in high field direction, are observed (Fig. 3). As against Duffy's⁶ observation for iron(III) dithiocarbamates, ¹H nmr signals

Fig. 3. ¹H NMR spectra of

Bi(dedtc)₃ = Tris(diethyl dithiocarbamato)bismuth(III).
 Bi(dipr dtc)₃ = Tris(di-n-propyl dithiocarbamato)bismuth(III).
 Bi(de)₂(dipr) = Bis(diethyl dithiocarbamato)di-n-propyl dithio-
 carbamato bismuth(III).

are found to move to their original regions with time where they are observed in parent complexes. This indicates that the ligand scrambling does occur in bismuth(III) dithiocarbamates but at a slower rate facilitating their separation by preparative tlc.

The foregoing observations show the existence of ligand scrambling among bismuth(III) dithiocarbamates in non-polar solvents (like benzene). So, the mixed ligand dithiocarbamates prepared by Kheiri *et al* through a circuitous route can be prepared by simple mixing of the individual symmetric chelates.

References

1. L. QUE, JR. and L. H. PIGNALET, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, 13, 351.
2. R. CHANT, A. R. HENDRICKSON, R. L. MARTIN and N. M. RHODE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, 14, 1894.
3. O. LISKA, J. LEHOTAY, E. BRANDSTETEROVA and G. GUIOCHON, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1979, 171, 153; 1979, 172, 379.
4. M. MORIYASU AND Y. HASHIMOTO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1980, 53, 3590.
5. E. BEINROHR and J. GARAJ, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1980, 45, 1785.
6. N. V. DUFFY, W. G. MOVIUS and D. L. UHRICH, *Inorg. Chim. Acta Lett.*, 1982, 64, L91.
7. J. STARY and J. RUZICKA, *Talanta*, 1968, 15, 505; 1967, 14, 909.
8. F. M. N. KHEIRI, C. A. TSIPIS and G. E. MANOUSSAKIS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1977, 25, 223.
9. D. COUCUVANIS, *Progr. Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, 11, 271.
10. S. AKERSTORM, *Arkiv., Kemi*, 1965, 24, 495.
11. C. A. TSIPIS and G. E. MANOUSSAKIS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, 18, 35.